

Grain yield (t/ha)

2. Simulated potential grain yields (rough rice, 14% moisture content) for different situations in Los Baños. The yield of weekly transplantings for 1988 are shown (•) The lines represent the yield levels that have a 10, 25, 75, and 90% probability to be exceeded (solid lines for 25 and 75%, broken lines for 10 and 90% probability).

conditions during the reproductive phase of rice development significantly affect grain yield.

Simulated potential yields can serve

as references for ongoing field trials and can facilitate interpretation of year-to-year or season-to-season differences in growth and yield. □

Grain quality

Effect of rice genotype x environment interactions on quality characters

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We tested five common rice varieties (H4, BG94-1, BG379-2, BW531, and BG34-6) at five locations in southern Sri Lanka in 1987 wet season. The locations were chosen to provide differences in annual rainfall. The cultivars were planted in a randomized

Range and analysis of variance for quality characteristics of 5 rice varieties in 5 rainfall environments. * Matara, Sri Lanka, 1987 wet season.

	Length:breadth ratio		Grain elongation (%)		Amylose (%)		Brown rice protein (%)		
Overall range		2.87-4.16		27.3-66.0		25.1-29.8		6.2-11.1	
Range of mean values		3.12-4.01		37.8-52.9		27.9-29.1		7.4- 8.8	
ANOVA									
Source	df	MS	F	MS	F	MS	F	MS	F
Varieties	4	0.5816	21.8***	156.6527	16.75***	1.3350	222.50***	1.8802	308.23***
Environments	4	0.0412	1.4 ns	196.5726	21.02***	1.3679	227.98***	2.2510	369.02***
Variety × environment	16	0.0426	1.0 ns	59.2172	6.33***	1.3228	222.13***	0.9585	157.13***
Heterogeneity	4	0.0715	2.1 ns	12.5252	0.17 ns	2.2118	2.13 ns	0.8325	0.83 ns
Residual deviations	12	0.0330	1.2 ns	74.7811	7.99***	1.0397	173.23***	1.0005	164.02***
Error	50	0.0267		9.3507		0.0060		0.0061	

* P < 0.05, ** P < 0.01, *** P < 0.001, ns = not significant.

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complete block design with three replications at each location.

Both variety and environment effects were significant for grain elongation, amylose, and brown rice protein, and the variety × environment interaction was significant (see table). This means the effects were not additive. Heterogeneity between linear regressions also was not significant. But highly significant values were found for residual deviations.

Grain elongation was highest in BG34-6 and lowest in BG94-1. BW531 showed the lowest amylose content and the highest brown rice protein. BG379-2 had the highest amylose content and BG34-6 the lowest brown rice protein. Length/breadth ratio was highest in BG94-1 and lowest in BW531.

Interactions between variety and environment for the characters studied cannot be explained by linear regression. This could be due to interactions that were specific to particular combinations. The length/breadth ratio did not show significant interaction with variety and environment. □